

Effects of submergence timing and application of azospirillum and K on direct seeded rice

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Farmers who depend on the Cauvery system in Tamil Nadu have been forced to direct seed rice because of frequent delays in receipt of canal water. K has been reported to help plants recover from

moisture stress by maintaining higher leaf expansion rates, higher chlorophyll contents, and stomatal resistance. It also promotes yield stability and increases productivity under moisture stress by synthesizing more proline. Azospirillum increases root proliferation and provides facilities to get through drought conditions by remaining in the root interspace.

We conducted an experiment to find out if K and azospirillum can be used to enhance productivity under restricted water conditions and to what extent submergence can be delayed after seeding.

The soil is sandy loam (Typic Haplustalf), with neutral pH, low available N and K, and medium P. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design during 1989-90 and 1990-91 monsoon seasons. ADT38 rice was the test variety. The main plot was submerged 30, 45, and 60 d after seeding (DAS) to simulate water receipt from the canal. Subplots were treated with K at different times with and without azospirillum inoculation. Nutrient levels were kept uniform at 150-26-50 kg NPK/ha. Rice received only rain until first submergence, after which it was kept wet.

Table 1. Effect of time of submergence (30, 45, 60 DAS) and application of azospirillum and K on grain yield of direct sown ADT38 rice. Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Treatment no.	Time of K application and azospirillum inoculation	Grain yield (t/ha)											
		1989-90				1990-91				Pooled data (mean of 2 yr)			
		30	45	60	Mean	30	45	60	Mean	30	45	60	Mean
1	100% K basal	5.2	4.8	4.5	4.8	4.6	4.8	4.2	4.6	4.9	4.8	4.4	4.1
2	1 + azospirillum	6.3	5.2	4.9	5.5	5.5	5.4	4.5	5.1	4.9	5.3	4.7	5.3
3	50% K basal + 25% at tillering + 25% at PI	4.9	5.2	4.7	4.9	5.0	4.8	3.8	4.6	4.9	5.0	4.2	4.7
4	3 + azospirillum	6.1	5.7	4.9	5.5	6.1	5.6	4.9	5.5	6.1	5.6	4.9	5.5
5	50% K basal + 50% at tillering	5.1	5.0	4.5	4.9	4.8	5.2	4.2	4.7	4.9	5.1	4.3	4.8
6	5 + azospirillum	5.6	5.5	4.9	5.3	5.6	5.6	5.1	5.5	5.6	5.6	5.0	5.4
7	50% K basal + 50% at PI	5.2	5.2	4.8	5.1	5.1	4.8	4.9	4.9	5.2	5.0	4.8	5.0
8	7 + azospirillum	5.9	6.0	5.3	5.7	5.7	5.5	5.4	5.5	5.8	5.7	5.4	5.6
	Mean	5.6	5.3	4.8	-	5.3	5.2	4.6	-	5.4	5.3	4.7	-
	Time of submergence	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD
	Time of K application and azospirillum	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3
	Interaction	0.3	ns	0.3	ns	0.2	ns	0.2	ns	0.2	ns	0.2	ns

^a ns = nonsignificant.

Table 2. Effect of time of submergence (30, 45, 60 DAS) and application of azospirillum and K on straw yield of direct sown ADT38 rice.

Treatment no.	Time of K application and azospirillum inoculation	Straw yield (t/ha)							
		1989-90				1990-91			
		30	45	60	Mean	30	45	60	Mean
1	100% K basal	5.61	5.23	5.02	5.29	5.59	5.16	4.70	5.15
2	1 + azospirillum	6.36	5.41	5.09	5.62	6.43	5.39	5.18	5.67
3	50% K basal + 25% at tillering + 25% at PI	5.49	5.44	5.04	5.32	5.31	5.51	4.86	5.73
4	3 + azospirillum	6.48	5.98	5.30	5.92	6.34	5.83	5.13	5.77
5	50% K basal + 50% at tillering	5.50	5.49	5.22	5.40	5.42	5.36	4.72	5.17
6	5 + azospirillum	5.98	5.73	5.12	5.61	5.99	5.62	5.03	5.55
7	50% K basal + 50% at PI	5.64	5.56	5.16	5.46	5.55	5.38	4.94	5.29
8	7 + azospirillum	6.32	6.17	5.74	6.08	6.29	6.18	5.63	6.03
	Mean	5.92	5.63	5.21	-	5.87	5.56	5.02	-
	Time of submergence	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD
	Time of K application and azospirillum	0.11	0.37	0.14	0.47	0.11	0.37	0.13	0.37
	Interaction	0.19	ns	0.23	ns	0.23	ns	0.23	ns

Submergence at 30 or 45 DAS produced optimum grain yield; further delay in irrigation water reduced yield (Table 1). Azospirillum exhibits an augmentative effect. Applying a split of K—half seeding, half at panicle initiation (PI)—benefited rice more than when all K was applied as basal or in three splits.

Straw yield followed a similar trend (Table 2).

Farmers can obtain higher productivity in direct seeded rice that is later converted to wet rice by applying irrigation water at 45 DAS, azospirillum inoculation, and K splits basal and at PI. □

Planting rainfed winter crops in rice fallows under different N and tillage treatments

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We evaluated the productivity and production economics of five winter crops sown in rice fallows under rainfed conditions before and after the harvest of transplanted irrigated rice under two tillage conditions and two N levels. Soil is clayey loam with a pH of 6.8, 0.6% organic C, 0.06% total N, 20 kg available P/ha, and 170 kg available K/ha. The experiment had 7.5- × 2.0-m plots laid out in a split-split-plot design with four replications. Tillage was in the main plots, crops in subplots, and N in sub-subplots.